
**Project SOP D-JRP17-
WP1.SOP3 – Standard
Operating procedure for
Serological diagnosis
Workpackage 1**

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: APHA, BfR, FLI, INIAV,
IZSAM, NDRVMI, INSA, WBVR

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	<i>Identification of <u>emerging Brucella</u> species: new threats for human and animals</i>
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP JRP-17 IDEMBRU
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2020
Duration	36 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project SOP	D-JRP17-WP1.SOP3 - Standard Operating procedure for Serological diagnosis
Project Acronym	IDEMBRU
Author	Ana Cristina Ferreira, Acacia Ferreira Vicente, Claire Ponsart
Other contributors	Vitomir Djokic, Luca Freddi, Roland Ashford, Adrian Whatmore, Sascha Al Dahouk, Dirk Hofreuter, Daniela Prasse, Falk Melzer, Sandra Cavaco, Giuliano Garofolo, Flavio Sacchini, Fabrizio De Massis, Katuscia Zilli, Mihail Milanov, Hristo Daskalov, Guillaume Girault
Due month of the report	31 – Decembre 2022
Actual submission month	April 2022
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	<i>OTHER</i> Save date: 26-Apr-23
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EMA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

--	--

STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE FOR SEROLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS

Scope

This document defines the serological diagnostic tests to be used as a first line approach to detect specific antibodies to smooth and rough *Brucella* species in animal serum samples. Several serological tests are available, including rapid agglutination tests (RSA), slow agglutination tests (SAT), complement fixation tests (CFT), lateral flow tests (LFT), and indirect enzyme-linked immunoassays (iELISA).

Collection and treatment of blood samples

A minimum of 1 mL blood sample should be collected and placed into a standard 5 mL dry tube. After collection of the whole blood, allow the blood to clot by leaving it undisturbed at room temperature. During storage and transport to the laboratory, samples should be kept at $5 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$.

Upon the reception at the laboratory, blood samples should be centrifuged 2500-3000 x rpm for 10 minutes in a refrigerated centrifuge. The resulting supernatant is designated serum.

Following centrifugation, immediately transfer the serum into a clean polypropylene tube. The samples should be maintained at $5 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$ while handling.

If cannot be processed within 24 h, it should be frozen at a temperature $\leq -16^\circ\text{C}$.

Each sample should be register within IDEMBRU project OHEJP-JRP19_MDB1 spreadsheet and the secondary code (serology) has to be assigned.

Smooth *Brucella* species

As all serological tests have limitations, especially when testing individual animals, more than one test should be performed in parallel.

Rose Bengal Test (RBT) is a rapid agglutination test, with a high diagnostic sensitivity (>98%) that detects specific antibodies to smooth *Brucella* species.

All serum samples should be firstly submitted to RBT for screening. The test is performed according to OIE/WOAH Terrestrial Manual 2022 (Brucellosis (infection with *Brucella abortus*, *B. melitensis* and *B. suis*, Chapter 3.1.4.) and to the brucellosis National Reference Laboratories (NRL) procedure.

Briefly, 25–30 μl of each serum sample on an enamel, glass or plastic plate, is mixed with an equal volume of antigen and after a 4-minute period agglutination is read. Any visible reaction is considered to be positive.

The complement fixation test (CFT) is more specific than the RBT. Can be used as a confirmatory test and should be applied to all samples. CFT is a quantitative method, and has a standardised system of unitage.

The test is performed according to OIE/WOAH Terrestrial Manual 2022 (Brucellosis - infection with *Brucella abortus*, *B. melitensis* and *B. suis*, Chapter 3.1.4.) and the brucellosis NRL procedure.

Other serological tests, such as **enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISAs)**, show good diagnostic performance, and are commercially available for different animal species. Usually ELISA tests are technically simpler to perform and more robust, and their use may be preferred.

However, as most of the available diagnostic tests are validated only for ruminants and suidae, the same procedures may be used for other animals' species, but each test should be validated for its fitness.

Rough *Brucella* species – *Brucella canis* diagnosis

Available methods for serological testing of *B. canis* infection in canids (domestic dogs, wolves, coyotes, foxes, jackals) include rapid slide agglutination test (RSAT), tube agglutination test (TAT), lateral flow immuno assay (LFIA), agar gel immunodiffusion (AGID), immune fluorescence assay (IFA), and indirect enzyme linked immunoassay (IELISA). The most used tests for routine diagnosis are RSAT, TAT and LFIA. All sera from canids should be tested at least by two different methods.